

When do consumers perceive supermarket chains as good corporate citizens? Evidence from the Dominican Republic during Covid-19

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The disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic have magnified the need to examine how corporate citizenship (CC) influences consumer behavior. This study extends the theory of planned behavior and tests the relative influence of four dimensions of CC on consumer planned intentions to buy (BI) and planned behavior (PB). It also examines whether consumer attitude towards business (CAB) moderates the relationships. Data were obtained from supermarket customers in the Dominican Republic and analyzed with confirmatory factor analysis and multiple regression analysis. The findings support the effect of CC on BI and PB, although the effects vary. BI is significantly influenced by three dimensions of CC, namely economic citizenship, legal citizenship, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. But these effects are weaker when CAB is low. Additionally, the moderating influence of CAB highlights that supermarket consumers are less influenced by CC activities when CAB is low.

Keywords: corporate citizenship, corporate social responsibility, theory of planned behavior, COVID-19

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Introduction

The COVID-19 global pandemic has threatened the value network of many businesses across several different sectors. The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly affected numerous organizations and companies (He & Harris 2020), including education, food, healthcare, tourism, retail, manufacturing, logistics, etc. For example, various studies have examined COVID-19's effect on the retail industry (Dominici et al. 2021, Wittwer & Anderson 2021). In addition, the pandemic has changed how businesses emphasize their position in society and how they seek their economic, social, and environmental goals. Now, companies should implement Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) strategies to demonstrate their commitment to society and vulnerable groups, particularly those closest to them, i.e., the local environment connected with the place of origin or territories where they have a more significant presence.

Nicola et al. (2020) suggest that the food sector and the healthcare industry are probably the most impacted by the pandemic. But, despite the devastation of the pandemic, supermarkets continue to provide services to satisfy essential needs. There is also more spending on food across all supermarket stores. Likewise, online merchants have seen a remarkable rise in customer spending on groceries. The Dominican Republic retail industry has also experienced significant changes during the past three decades. This transition occurred due to continued economic development, as shown by changing retail forms, shop sizes, and product and service diversity. As a result, retail, particularly supermarket chains, expanded their operations and services (USDA 2018). The number of supermarket operators in the Dominican Republic has increased by 100 percent in the past twenty years. Supermarkets chains are in Santo Domingo and other major cities. More than 120 supermarkets in the Dominican Republic belong to supermarket chains (USDA 2018).

This study contributes to the extant body of literature because it is a pioneering study that evaluates the influences of CC on the theory of planned behavior (TPB) in times of a pandemic, with consumer attitude toward business (ATB) acting as a moderator. ATB refers to how a person has either a positive or a negative assessment/appraisal of business conduct to be performed upon (Taylor & Todd 1995). This research investigates what supermarket consumers in the Dominican Republic think about the CC of supermarket chains during a pandemic and how those practices and strategies influence their planned behavior (PB).

Literature Review

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

The TPB advanced by Ajzen (1985) and Ajzen (2011) serves as an essential foundation for this research. TPB models human behavior and has been extensively employed in various disciplines, including health, marketing, international business, education, etc. The primary tenet of the TPB is that an individual's conduct is governed by a purpose, which comprises three constructs: (1) attitude toward behavior (ATB), (2) subjective norm (SN), and (3) perceived behavioral control (PBC).

In general terms, ATB is an evaluation or response to engaging in a specific activity, such as being pleased or sad, favorable or unfavorable. It may also be defined as either worthless or helpful. Individuals' intentions to engage in a specific activity are strengthened by their favorable attitudes about that behavior (Beck & Ajzen 1991). SN refers to social pressure to do or abstain from acting (Ajzen 1985) and denotes an impression of the expectations of significant others. PBC is related to perceived self-efficacy, which is concerned with the judgment of how well one can execute required actions to deal with specific situations (Fishbein & Ajzen 2009). These three elements contribute to developing a behavioral intention, which measures an individual's desire to engage in a particular action.

Despite the extensive use of the TPB, some researchers have criticized its predictive efficacy, primarily because of a small set of variables to explain behavior in determining circumstances (Tommasetti et al. 2018). In that tenor, some scholars have made changes to the original TPB model by adding more variables such as *perceived ease of use*, *personal moral norm*, *refusal skill*, *perceived moral obligation*, *past behavior*, *perceived usefulness*, etc. This research added to the TPB model the CC's variables of economic citizenship (EC), legal citizenship (LC), ethical citizenship (ETC), discretionary citizenship (DC), and attitude towards business (CAB).

This research is related to aspects of supermarket chains' CC policies and customers' perceptions about the performance of these entities fulfilling them during the COVID-19 pandemic. Scholars agree that it is not enough to assess supermarket's performance solely based on economic and financial statements; it is necessary to consider their contributions to social and environmental sustainability as a strategic element to improve customers' perceptions through different actions and strategies which can affect society and the environment (Emese 2018).

Additionally, Dennis et al. (2009) pose that the concept of corporate giving or philanthropy has been the subject of many debates. Friedman (2002) considers social responsibility activities as demands on resources that affect investors' interests. In other words, managers will consider altruistic actions acceptable if they positively impact financial statements. On the other hand, Dönmez-Maç et al. (2019) believe that companies must assume corporate philanthropy based on moral and ethical terms above economic interests because companies are members of society and have a duty to use their resources for the betterment of the common good of society at large. Although CSR and its implications have been widely studied, the same has not happened with the decision-making processes related to behaviors motivated by philanthropy. Sánchez (2000) indicates that behaviors motivated by philanthropy are intended to enhance the firm's financial performance or used as a political response to pressures exerted by environmental actors. Conversely, Dönmez-Maç et al. (2019) point out that corporate altruism is exhibited when corporations assign part of their resources to promote the overall welfare of society, no matter if the actions improve profits or enhance corporate images. But CC is unlikely to be entirely explained by strategic and altruistic factors and may include other factors such as the extent of a CEO's behavioral control, the degree to which they consider corporate philanthropy a component of their self-identity, and firms' availability of resources.

Figure 1. Research Model Showing the Effect of TPB and CC on BI and the Moderating Role of CAB on the BI-PB Relationship

Source: the authors

Fishbein & Ajzen (2009) determined that certain decision-making contexts require moral considerations, while Conner & Armitage (1998) identified self-identity as a component of TPB. Similarly, Dennis et al. (2009) argued that individuals are more inclined to engage in a specific behavior if this is considered an

essential component of their self-identity. Consequently, it is necessary to evaluate customers' perceptions about CC (strategic or altruist), considering the different TPB components: ATB, SN, and PBC.

Figure 1 details the research constructs and hypothesized relationships on the elements of the TPB and the CC on the BI. It also shows the moderating effect of the CAB on the relationship between BI and PB.

Attitude toward Behavior (ATB)

Attitude relates to an individual's judgment of the desired conduct (positive or negative) and refers to a subjective assessment of behavior (Fishbein & Ajzen 2009). Additionally, it may be defined as the subjective assessment of conduct (Farah & Newman 2010). In other words, it involves thinking about the consequences of carrying out a behavior. Within the TPB, an individual's attitude toward a particular activity is determined by behavioral beliefs and result assessment. Further, the attitude construct serves as an immediate antecedent that predicts an individual's desire to participate in determined actions (Ajzen 2011). In consumer psychology research, attitude has traditionally been a critical factor in determining behavioral intention and actual action. In retail, attitudes about CC have long been a crucial component in accurately forecasting pre-environmental market intention and demand. Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1. ATB is positively related to BI.

Subjective Norms (SN)

Fishbein & Ajzen (2009) define SN as a belief regarding whether most people approve or reject certain conduct. Zhang et al. (2019) stated that SN relates to the social stress experienced by individuals in the immediate environment and those vital to a customer's life. Additionally, it reflects how much someone feels ethically responsible for others by purchasing sustainable products (Barber et al. 2014). SN are views about whether other significant individuals, such as family and friends, accept or disapprove of one's actions. SN are established by an individual's normative standards and is an incentive to adhere to certain behaviors. When a person intends to participate in a specific activity, SN serves as a direct antecedent (Beck & Ajzen 1991). Scalco et al. (2017) discovered that SN has more relevance and favorable impacts on purchasing intentions using TPB. Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H2. SN is positively related to BI.

Perceived Behavioral Control (PBC)

Beck & Ajzen (1991) defined PBC as an individual's assessment of the amount of difficulty in doing an activity of interest. According to Al-Swidi et al. (2014), this is a person's decision on whether they can engage in certain conduct. Specifically, people's knowledge of available resources, such as buying products from supermarket chains, could be more expensive in times of a pandemic. Perceptions of how difficult or easy a purchase will influence consumers' actual behavior. Bandura (2012) determined that perceived self-efficacy is comparable to PBC and amplifies the concept, stating that PBC is subject to change based on the situation and consumers' opinions of their behavioral control and time level. For example, cultural and environmental factors could influence consumers from different countries. The literature suggests that PBC, together with the other two TPB components, ATB and SN, is a significant latent variable determining the retailer's selection (Al-Swidi et al. 2014). Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H3. PBC is positive related to BI.

Buying Intention (BI)

Fazio & Zanna (1981) indicated that attitude is the memory connection between a particular item and a quick judgment. Thus, attitude may provide insight into customers' psychological evaluations of items (Chen et al. 2020). Mostafa (2006) discovered a positive association between attitude and BI across various cultures. Consumer satisfaction has been an area of significant development amongst academia during the pandemic. Rukuni & Maziriri (2020) indicated that several studies have focused on this topic. The authors examined the impact of COVID-19 readiness strategies on customer satisfaction and the consequences for consumer behavioral intentions. The COVID-19 effect on society and consumers altered consumers' product needs, shopping, purchasing behavior, and post-purchase satisfaction levels (Mason et al. 2020). On the other hand, Monmousseau et al. (2020), in their research focusing on customer satisfaction, provided an overview of retail practices during the pandemic and derived an action plan for maintaining satisfaction, trust, and loyalty during COVID-19. Findings show that keeping in touch with customers over digital channels generates an attitude that significantly affects accepting certain behavioral choices (Zhou et al. 2013). Prior studies have also focused on the association between attitude and deliberate conduct. For example, Peña-García et al. (2020) found that environmental sentiments have a role in customers' propensity to buy. Attitude is one of the essential elements in determining whether customers are willing to buy from supermarkets, according to Foabeh & Achaleke (2020). So our next hypothesis is:

H4. BI is positive related to PB.

Corporate Citizenship (CC)

Corporate Citizen refers to the set of socioeconomic activities frequently taken by companies to fulfill perceived social responsibilities (Carroll 1998). Crane & Matten (2005) iterate that CC is concerned with the well-being of people and the environment, which results in the development of value for the company and define CC as corporate contributions and other acts of generosity in the local community. Similarly, Maignan et al. (1999) described CC as how businesses meet the economic, legal, ethical, and discretionary responsibilities imposed on them by their stakeholders.

The adoption of CC may result in the capacity to attain corporate financial success (Camacho & Salazar-Concha 2020). But, on the other hand, its implementation contributes to increased customer purchase intention (Lee & Yoon 2018), employee job satisfaction, work engagement, organizational citizenship, and company success (Lin et al. 2012). CC encompasses a range of activities, including funding staff education, promoting ethical programs, adopting environmentally responsible practices, and the sponsorship of community events (Maignan & Ferrell 2000).

Corporations ought to be more aware of how they appear to society as having adopted corporate citizenship initiatives to show that they operate in a socially responsible way (Carrigan et al. 2017). The advantages of civic engagement, nevertheless, are somewhat conflicting. While some research show businesses/retailers induce a favorable behavioral reaction in consumers others contend that consumer responses are not as straightforward (Luo & Bhattacharya 2006). Given these inconsistencies, further research is required into how customers react ethically to companies claiming to be corporate citizens, especially when society faces a crisis or pandemic (Marquina Feldman & Vasquez-Parraga 2013).

Economic Citizenship (EC)

The EC dimension requires that all businesses manufacture, market, and supply high-quality items profitably. In a larger sense, businesses must be successful and provide essential commodities and services to society (Carroll 1998). Corporate citizens who behave ethically generate enough money to ensure that their investors enjoy a healthy return on their investment. Other stakeholders are guaranteed the business's continuation via the flow of goods, services, employment, and other advantages supplied

by the firm. Profitable firms can meet the needs and desires of their shareholders, which makes economic trade attractive from a social standpoint (Camacho & Salazar-Concha 2020).

H5. EC has a positive effect on BI.

Legal Citizenship (LC)

This CC dimension refers to the organizational obligation to obey the law (Carroll 1998). As with ordinary citizens, good corporate citizens must consider the law. The law may be seen as codified ethics (Camacho & Salazar-Concha 2020). If business ethics is about doing what is right, legislators set minimal requirements for how these principles should be exhibited in corporate success. These rules are relevant to firms seeking to be good corporate citizens since they govern their interactions with major stakeholders such as customers, workers, and the natural environment (Maignan et al. 1999).

H6. LC has a positive effect on BI.

Ethical Citizenship (EC)

In this dimension of CC, the aim is the organizational obligation to conduct moral business activities. Compliance with the law requires working at the bare minimum level of permitted behavior (Maignan & Ferrell 2000). The law is frequently stated to be the foundation of good conduct. To be a good corporate citizen, a company must do more than follow the law. Rules and regulations usually represent the bare minimums to which legislators can agree in political maneuvering (Lee & Carroll 2011). Nowadays, many individuals raise concerns about society's morals (Carroll 1998). They apply not just to business but also to other areas of society, government, education, healthcare, etc. Companies that aspire to be recognized as exemplary corporate citizens must demonstrate economic success, compliance with the law, and a commitment to operating ethically.

H7. EC has a positive effect on BI.

Discretionary Citizenship (DC)

Maignan & Ferrell (2003) define discretionary citizenship as transparent business practices based on moral ideals that assist the organization in achieving community recognition and accomplishment. This dimension focus on the organizational duty to engage in a non-statutory activity. Philanthropy is widely thought to benefit humanity via charitable activities, regardless of whether individual persons, foundations, or companies are involved (Maignan et al. 1999). Philanthropy, which is commonly exhibited via corporate donations, is frequently equated with Corporate Citizenship by many in the business sector (Carroll 1998). These days, there are various methods by which companies are giving back to the communities in which they operate, benefiting all stakeholders. Although economic methods are not the only ones, corporations can support social activities, education, and environmental protection can be considered part of these practices.

H8. DC has a positive effect on BI.

Attitude toward Business (CAB)

Attitude is a significant predictor of behavioral adoption intention (Fishbein 1980). It comprises an individual's central beliefs about the perceived consequences of engaging in a particular behavior (Al-Debei et al. 2013). According to the TPB, an individual's inner views about the results of a specific action affect attitudes toward the actual conduct (Ajzen 1985). Individuals' beliefs vary depending on their own experiences, personality traits, and mentalities (Al-Lozi 2011).

Behavior is based on an attitude. According to original research performed by Vitell et al. (2005), individual attitudes are essential to understanding consumer ethical decision-making. The authors showed that consumer attitude toward business is a significant predictor of the passive component of ethical problems. The authors concluded that individuals' opinions about business connect to their views about dealing with morally ambiguous customer problems. Consumers with a more unfavorable attitude toward business were less likely to consider certain dubious activities to be unethical. Studies on the effect of corporate attitudes on consumer ethics have generated inconsistent findings, which highlights the need for further research (Patwardhan et al. 2012).

H9. CAB moderates the relationship between BI and PB.

Methodology

Sample and Procedure

Following COVID-19-related limitations imposed by the government of the Dominican Republic, a survey was undertaken, and questionnaires were sent to students at one of the country's most prestigious institutions of higher learning. Student samples are widely used in consumer behavior research given the cost and access benefits (Yim et al. 2014). For this study, university students qualify as an appropriate sample for hypothesis testing given the high degree of within-group homogeneity (Peterson 2001). Survey Monkey was selected because it enables participants to complete the instrument using various technological devices and facilitates data collection. Translations were made from English to Spanish and then back to English by researchers proficient in both languages. The differences and similarities between the two forms of the English language were explored to ensure validity of the translation process. Only 206 of the 396 questionnaires received were included in the data analysis, resulting in a response rate of 52%.

Measures and Sample Characteristics

The questionnaire consisted of four sections. The first section measured the three components of TPB (ATB, SN and PBC) on a 7-point Likert scale (Ajzen 2002). The second section of the questionnaire was based on CC using an 18-item measure created by Maignan and Ferrell (2000). This scale offers a measure of each of the four Perceived Corporate Citizenship categories at the organizational level and a composite score. The third component measured ATB is the Richins (1983) scale. The final section collected demographic information.

The sample represented both gender groups, with males accounting for 52.7% and females 47.3%. Similarly, the different age groups were well-represented, with the most significant category ranging between 25-34 years old. Most participants have a postgraduate degree (47%) and visit a supermarket every week (45%).

Analyses and Results

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Following the guidelines provided by Hair et al. (2010), confirmatory factor analysis facilitated the construction of factor scores for hypothesis testing. The analysis followed the procedures specified by Rambocas & Mahabir (2021). All indicators satisfied the retention criteria in EC, LC, ETC, and DC. For ATB, one item was deleted because of low factor loadings. Similarly, one item was deleted from BI, PB, and CAB scales. The analysis on SN revealed a two-factor solution with acceptable variance explained and reliability coefficients. Our subsequent analysis retained the two-factor solution and expanded the details of our model. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Results of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Variable	# of Items	Factor Loadings	% of Variance explained	Composite Reliability
Economic Citizenship (EC)	4	.69 .83 .81 .77	60.87	.86
Legal Citizenship (LC)	4	.79 .83 .83 .82	66.68	.89
Ethical Citizenship (ETC)	5	.82 .75 .83 .72 .68	58.01	.87
Discretionary Citizenship (DC)	5	.77 .80 .84 .77 .84	65.03	.90
Attitude Toward Behavior (ATB)	3	.68 .84 .80	60.57	.82
Subjective Norms – First Factor (SN1 and SN 4)	2	.81 .81	65.80	.79
Subjective Norms – Second Factor (SN2 and SN3)	2	.81 .81	65.59	.79
Buying Intentions (BI)	2	.94 .94	88.55	.94
Perceived Behavioral Control (PBC)	3	.84 .89 .87	75.41	.90
Planned Behavior (PB)	2	.88 .88	77.95	.88
Consumer Attitude Towards Business (CAB)	2	.81 .81	64.87	.79

Hypotheses Testing: Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA), and Moderated Analysis

MRA was used to test the expected relationships among the theoretical constructs. The analytical models are specified in variates 1 to 3.

$$Y_{BI} = b_0 + b_1X_{EC} + b_2X_{LC} + b_3X_{ETC} + b_4X_{DC} + b_5X_{ATB} + b_6X_{SN_1} + b_7X_{SN_2} + b_8X_{PBC} \quad [\text{Model 1}]$$

$$Y_{PB} = b_0 + b_1X_{BI} + b_2X_{CAB} \quad [\text{Model 2}]$$

$$Y_{PB} = b_0 + b_1X_{BI} + b_2X_{CAB} + b_3X_{BI}X_{CAB} \quad [\text{Model 3}]$$

Table 2. Results of Multiple Regression Analysis

	Standardized β	p	R^2	df	F	p
Model 1						
Economic citizenship (EC)	.03	.68	.27	(8, 197)	9.10	.00
Legal citizenship (LC)	-.21	.03				
Ethical citizenship (ETC)	.21	.03				
Discretionary citizenship (DC)	-.13	.13				
Attitude toward behavior (ATB)	-.12	.12				
Subjective norms1 (SN_1)	-.07	.38				
Subjective norms2 (SN_2)	.25	.00				
Perceived behavior control (PBC)	-.29	.00				
Model 2						
Intention (BI)	.73	.00	.54	(2, 203)	118.82	.00
Attitude toward business (CAB)	.22	.00				
Model 3						
Intention (BI)	.75	.00	.57	(1, 202)	88.09	.00
Attitude toward business (CAB)	.22	.00				
Moderator (Intention*Attitude toward business) (BI*CAB)	.17	.00				

Figure 2. Moderating Effects of CAB

The moderator analysis also shows that the relationship between BI and PB is stronger for higher levels of CAB. A comparison is shown in Figure 2. Overall, the results support the influence of CC on the TPB. Relatively to predicting BI, Model 1 explains 27% of the variance ($R^2=.27$; $F(8, 197)=9.10$, $p=.00$). Surprisingly, only four of the independent variables exhibit significant influence which include LC ($\beta=-.21$, $p=.03$), EC ($\beta=.21$, $p=.03$), SM_2 ($\beta=.25$, $p=.00$), and PBC ($\beta=-.29$, $p=.00$). PBC has the strongest influence

on BI, followed by SM2, EC, and LC. Model 2 also meritoriously predict PB accounting for 53.9% of the overall variance ($R^2=.54$; $F(2, 203)=188.82$, $p=.00$). The results show that both BI ($\beta=.73$, $p=.00$) and ETC ($\beta=.22$, $p=.00$) significantly explain PB. The moderating effect of CAB is detailed in variate 3. The results from the regression analysis support the significant moderating effect of CAB on the relationship between BI and PB ($\Delta R^2=.03$, $\Delta F(1, 202)=12.82$, $p=.00$; and the percentage of variance increased to 56.7%. The results are presented in Table 2.

Discussion and Implications

The economic and social uncertainties from the COVID-19 pandemic have magnified the need for organizations to manage their CC activities effectively. This study examined how CC practice by supermarket chains in the Dominican Republic affects consumer planned behavior. The study's findings significantly link consumers' purchase intentions and behavior to two aspects of CC: the economic and legal, and two dimensions of the TPB: SN and PBC. Further, the study extended the TPB and showed that CAB moderates the relationship between consumers' intention and behavior. More specifically, the association is more robust when CAB is favorable. The statistically significant relationships of EC and LC suggest that consumers' purchase intentions and behavior are enhanced when supermarkets meet their economic and legal responsibilities. Consequently, to develop better performance and manage the uncertainties of the pandemic, supermarkets must be able to demonstrate a more profound commitment to customer service and contractual obligations to all stakeholders, including customers and employees. The study also shows that consumers' planned purchase intentions and behaviors are influenced by how supermarkets are perceived as responsible in their corporate behavior. From the arguments made in the TPB, these perceptions are usually based on subjective norms that arise from interpersonal relationships and social encounters. The findings also support PBC in consumer purchase intentions and behavior and demonstrate supermarkets' importance in facilitating easy access to information about their CC initiatives. The results show that the more consumers are aware of the CSR initiatives of supermarkets, the higher is their planned purchase behavior. This suggests that CSR initiatives during the COVID-19 pandemic should be treated as of paramount importance, and they share information about the supermarket's initiatives.

The study also supports the moderating effects of CAB on consumers' planned behavior. More specifically, consumers' sentiments towards businesses significantly changed consumer responses towards supermarkets. This finding supports our previous expectations that consumers with more favorable attitudes towards firms are more likely to respond positively to supermarkets' CC initiatives and reinforce the existing literature (Patwardhan et al. 2012).

Conclusions and Limitations

This study contributes to the field of CC, both in academia and practice, particularly in retail supermarket shopping behavior. From an academic and theoretical perspective, this study responds to essential calls that encourage researching the potential drivers of consumers' attitudes toward CC and TPB and the importance of creating a positive attitude toward enterprises to be favored by consumers. Although this research is regarded as pioneering because two constructs were evaluated, CC and TPB, in times of a pandemic, the empirical results are consistent with previous research findings and close the gaps identified in this research. This is thought to have contributed to enhancing and extending the understanding of the importance of creating a CC that can positively influence the TPB and improve the acceptance of supermarkets amongst consumers. This paper attempts to examine an integrated model of consumers' attitudes toward supermarket chains in the Dominican Republic from a practical perspective. Therefore, policymakers, managers, and other practitioners can benefit from the findings of this study in designing their CC strategies and programs to achieve long-term objectives. This study contributes to the

existing body of knowledge from a theoretical perspective by developing and testing a conceptual model that evaluates how much CC influences TPB when a health and economic crisis affects consumers. This model introduced several constructs and, at the same time, justified relationships among relevant constructs. The study also provides further validation for many structural relationships between constructs in a developing country context, the Dominican Republic.

Despite the significance of this study, as it is one of only a few to date that has examined the relationship between CC and TPB in times of a pandemic, this study has some limitations that can be addressed by future research. The first and most significant limitation is the sample; future studies should increase the number of participants and compare different market segments and/or countries to evaluate the implications and results based on cultural context, types of political systems, religion, and developing, emerging, and developed markets. Future researchers can expand on this study by comparing the results to other business sectors and countries.

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